

THE TITLE OF AN ARTICLE IN INDONESIAN CANNOT BE MORE THAN 15 WORDS, AND THE TITLE OF THE ARTICLE IN ENGLISH CANNOT BE MORE THAN 12 WORDS. TITLE PRINTED IN CAPITAL LETTERS (CENTER), WITH A LETTER SIZE OF 14 POINTS

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: Oleh karena itu pengajaran matematika sepatasnya diarahkan untuk memadukan kedua hal tersebut, antara konsep matematika secara formal yang diperoleh didalam sekolah dan konsep matematika di dunia nyata yang diperoleh diluar sekolah. Untuk itu dibutuhkan sesuatu yang dapat menghubungkan kedua hal tersebut antara matematika yang ada di luar sekolah dengan matematika yang di pelajari didalam sekolah. Salah satunya alternatifnya adalah dengan memanfaatkan pendekatan etnomatematika. Abstracts and keywords are written in English (and attached in Indonesian). The length of each abstract is 100-250 words. The abstract contains the essence of the entire contents of the writing presented clearly, whole and complete. The abstract is not a copy of the conclusion. The components contained in the abstract are IMRAD (Introduction, Methods, Result, And Discussion). The introduction is an explanation of the main reasons for the research. Methods are an explanation of how research works. The result is an explanation of the results obtained in the study. Discussion is the conclusion of the research.

Keywords: should in the word form or phrase which is contained in 4-6 words/phrase..

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2. Articles are written using standard Indonesian rules (EYD) with a variety of scientific writings, not a variety of popular scientific works and oral communication.
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Introduction

The introduction section contains the background, research context, and the results of the library study. Provide an introduction to the substance of the manuscript according to the topics and reasons of both theoretical and practical behind the writing of the script. Contains explicitly with a brief and clear direction, intent, purpose, novelty, and usefulness of the manuscript. A brief description of what other researchers have done/discovered before. Then the description of the problem to be examined. Antacids on other research related to results and it is better to postpone in Discussion.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method section contains exposure in the form of paragraphs about the approach or type of research, data source, data collection techniques, and data analysis that is manifestly performed by researchers, with a length of 5-10% of the total length of the article. Any measurement results reported in the Results section should be known the method used to obtain those results. The use of standard procedures can be referred to only. The description of the method is written in this Methods section. Describe the statistical analysis procedure used. The use of supporting instruments (table, diagram) is equipped with reference sources or information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research of results section contains exposure to the results of the analysis related to research questions. Any research results should be discussed. The discussion contains the meaning of results and comparison with the theory and/or the results of similar research. Length of exposure to results and discussion of 75-85% of the total length of the article. If results are separate from the discussion, the Results section only presents the results of research without having to discuss, new discussions are conducted in Discussion. Start systematically writing results. Do not present images from table data (use only one).

The information presented must be arranged in sequence and accordance with the hierarchy of the theory. If you want to emphasize the results obtained, it should be presented in the form of other numbers for example in the form of percentages or differences. If you want to show the number in question, just refer to the table that contains the number. Discussions need to be written in clear language and do not use sentences which are too long.

Similar research groups can be referred to in groups. Discussion presentation should also have a systematic flow, do not discuss an aspect over and over again. Use a systematic frame of mind so that the discussion will end to a point that will support the conclusion. The implications of research (theoretical and application) need to be emphasized in the discussion.

In tables, 12 font sizes can be used (or adjusted) and vertical lines should not be drawn. The number of tables and headings must be written above the table.

Tabel 3. The result of pre-teacher pont (IPK)

Categories	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Variance
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	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
High	8	91	95	93.25	0.6196	1.7536	3.071
Medium	9	88	91	89.89	0.3514	1.0540	1.111
Low	8	75	88	83.63	1.8987	5.3702	28.839

In pictures, the number of images and titles must be written below the image.

Picture 1. Problem Understanding Stage Completion Percentage
CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The conclusion/closing section contains research findings in the form of answers to research questions or the form of the essence of the discussion results. Inferences are presented in paragraph form. The conclusion is not the "copy" of the discussion. In taking conclusions do not speculate. Conclusions should be based on the facts of the research results

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

An acknowledgement is placed before the library list. It is necessary to mention the granting institution (along with the contract number) as documentation. Recognition of contributions of individuals or institutions that are meaningful in the implementation of research and writing.

REFERENCES:

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7. The Reference List is organized in an ordinance such as the following example and sorted alphabetically and chronologically.

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INTERNET (PERSONAL E-MAIL):

Naga, D. S. (ikip-jkt@indo.net.id). 1 Oktober 1997. *Artikel untuk JIP*. E-mail kepada Ali Saukah (jippsi@mlg.ywcn.or.id).